

**FOOD, HEALTH AND ENVIRONMENT RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES
TO TACKLE EMERGING PRIORITIES**

**Deliverable 1.2
Data management plan**

TECHNICAL REFERENCES

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Summary

The Data Management Plan is a mandatory deliverable by the European Commission (EC) that has to be tailored to the specific project activities and which should outline the strategies and procedures for managing the data generated and collected during the course of the project. The overarching goal of FHERITALE is to set the ground for providing the European scientific community with easily accessible services at a single entry point (a one-stop shop) enabling the research community to study and analyze the impact of artificial materials (including plastics, micro-, nano-, and biotechnological materials) on life, both directly and indirectly through their effect on health, food, and the environment.

Although the FHERITALE project will not generate sensitive data, to achieve its goal it will carry on activities involving the storage of survey data, deliverables, dissemination materials and personal information. The following sections describe how these research (and non-research) outputs will be managed alongside the duration of the project following the principle of open science, adhering and promoting FAIR principle. A revision of this document will be done at M18 and M30.

1. Data Summary

The FHERITALE project has not and will not deal with sensitive data or data of high economic value. It will generate the following types of data:

- Survey data: responses collected from survey participants.
- Deliverables: project outputs such as reports, presentations and publications presenting the findings, mappings and analyses carried out.
- Project dissemination materials: text and images on project website and social media channels.
- Consortium meeting notes and other internal administrative data.
- Personal information: names, email addresses and affiliations of the consortium members and other individuals (e.g., advisors) related to the project.

All these data will be stored in digital formats. Survey data and personal information will primarily be in structured formats such as spreadsheets, while deliverables and reports may include file types such as PDFs and text documents.

2. Fair data

2.1 Making data findable

Survey data and project related documents will be stored in Google Drive, which is chosen as the primary platform for data storage and collaboration due to its robust security measures and compliance with regulatory standards, ensuring adequate protection.

All produced documents will adopt a clear naming based on best practices. Documents will be assigned to a work package and will include information as part of version control. Public deliverables and position papers will be made available in public archives providing Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) or on Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/>).

2.2 Making data accessible

Deliverables will be also stored in the previous Google Drive shared folder and eventually will be made public and disseminated through the project website.

Survey data will be collected using tools such as Google Forms and the results will be securely stored in a shared Google Drive folder whose access is restricted to the project partners.

Finally, personal information, solely collected for the purpose of project communication, will be placed in the same shared folder.

Access to survey data, meeting notes, administrative data and other personal information will be restricted to authorized project team members only, defined by the project Coordination Team, in accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and other relevant data protection laws.

2.3 Making data interoperable

FHERITALE does not produce scientific data. Nonetheless, it will apply best practice in order to make the collected data interoperable and provide access to project results.

2.4 Increase data re-use

The project data will be preserved and shared as follows:

- Survey data and personal information will be securely deleted once it is no longer for project purposes.
- Deliverables will be made accessible to project stakeholders and collaborators through scientific community portals following project completion.
- Scientific publications such as papers and posters will be disseminated through the project website as well as through scholarly communication channels, e.g., Publishers/Journals websites, Institutional Repositories, scholarly communication networks (ResearchGate, Google Scholar) and other databases, identified by a DOI, which will make them more findable.

3. Allocation of resources

Research Infrastructures partners of the FHERITALE project will ensure that data generated by the project will be long term preserved (e.g. through Data Storage at SharePoint hosted by Instruct-ERIC).

For documents that will be stored on Zenodo, which ensures that they will be accessible after the end of the project (for at least 10 years), no resources are necessary since no fees are due up to 50 GB.

4. Data security

As already pointed above, all data will be stored in trusted repositories (Zenodo or the BMRB). The project will not deal with sensitive data or data of economic value.

5. Legal compliance with non-EU countries

Activities undertaken in non-EU countries, including the UK, will adhere to EU laws and provisions regarding data protection and ethical standards.

Opinions and approvals from local ethics committees and competent authorities will be obtained as required by national/EU legislation.

6. Ethical considerations

All data collection and storage procedures will comply with relevant ethical guidelines and regulations.

Informed consent will be obtained from survey participants prior to data collection, and measures will be taken to anonymize and de-identify data when necessary.

An Ethics Advisor with relevant scientific background will be appointed at the earliest possible stage of the project.

7. Data Management Plan review

The Data Management Plan will be reviewed and updated as necessary throughout the duration of the project. Therefore two updated reports will be delivered on months 18 and 30.